

REFORM IDEAS OF ABDURAUUF FITRAT

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Abstract. In this article, political scientist Abdurauf Fitrat from Bukhara pays special attention to the Jadidism movement and its essence in the Emirate of Bukhara.

Key words: Abdurauf Fitrat, education, school, madrasa, Turkestan, Bukhara, hurriyat, Faizulla Khojaev, Polvonniyoz Yusupov, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, republic.

The Jadidist movement that arose in the Emirate of Bukhara was essentially a political movement, and at first it fought for the fundamental reform of education, schools and madrasas, to change the educational system, and to awaken the nation to the meaning.

Jadidism is a movement based on global social and national values, and it was formed as a movement that responded to the interests of the local indigenous people of Central Asia and could fully satisfy the ripe needs of social development. It has followed a complex path of development from enlightenment to a powerful political movement. This movement has passed two stages in its history: the first is the enlightenment stage, and the second is the political stage. But it can be said that the views of the Jadids on the issue of statehood began to take shape in the first period and took a definite form in the second period. Mahmudhoja Behbudi and Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, who were considered leaders of the Turkestan jadid movement, played the role of unifying and cementing the jadids. In Bukhara, Fayzulla Khojaev and Abdurauf Fitrat, and in the Khanate of Khiva, Polvonniyoz Yusupov led this movement. [1]

With the goal of freeing Bukhara from medieval backwardness and religious superstition, reforming the Sharia, spreading enlightenment to the people, building

a free and prosperous society by establishing a constitutional monarchy and parliament, and later a democratic republic, introducing a national currency and forming a national army. prominent representatives of the Bukhara resistance movement - Abdulvahid Burkhanov (1875-1934), Mukamil Burkhanov (1884-1937), Sadriddin Ainiy (1878-1954), Abdurauf Fitrat (1886-1938), Faizulla Khojaev (1896-1938), Usman Khoja (1878-1968), Otaulla Khojaev (1880-1937), Abdugadir Muhiddinov (1892-1934), Musa Saidjonov (1893-1937), Qilich Khojaev (1896-1937) and others.[2] Ahmadjon Hamdiy, Hamidkhoja Mehriy, Muhyiddin Raf'at, Muhyiddin Mansurov, Mukhtar Saidjonov also actively participated in this movement.

Among them, Fitrat son of Abdurauf Abdurahim (1886-1938. Abdurauf Fitrat was born in Bukhara in 1886 in the family of a small merchant. His mother, Mustafabibi, was a very knowledgeable woman. Fitrat studied at the Mir Arab madrasa in Bukhara) was distinguished from others by his activity, reformism and ideological views on the renewal of society. He wrote works and poems such as "A Discussion on the Method of a Mudarris from Bukhara with a Farangi in India" (1909, Istanbul), "Statement of an Indian Tourist" (1912), "Rahbari Najot" (1913), "Family" (1916, Baku). widely propagated the ideas of Jadidism through

About this F. Khojaev writes in the work "On the history of the revolution in Bukhara and the national demarcation of Central Asia": *“Fitratning asarlari har qancha ta’qirlab qo’yilganiga qaramay keng tarqaldi, jamiyatning hamma tabaqalari orasida bu kitobchalar zo’r qiziqish bilan o’qildi, ular ustida bahs va munozaralar bo’lib turdi... vatanparvarlik she’rlar to’plami bo’lgan “Sayha”ni o’qigan kishilarni Buxoro hukumatigina emas, shu bilan birga rus hukumati ham ta’qib qila boshladi. Chunki bu she’rlarda Buxoro mustaqilligi g’oyasi birinchi marta yorqin shaklda ifodalab berildi”*. [3]

In his works, Fitrat criticized the evils in society and showed ways to get rid of them. The goals and tasks of the young progressives who worked in Bukhara were expressed in his work "Munozara". The Japanese researcher of Fitrat's works said

this. Komatsu said: *“1911 yilda Istanbulga o‘qishga borgan yosh buxorolik jadid Abdurauf Fitrat “Munozara” nomli forsha adabiy asar yozdi. Bu asar o‘sha davrda usuli jadid maktablarining zarurati hamda buxorolik islohotchilar bilan qadimchilar o‘rtasidagi tortishuvlarga nuqta qo‘yish uchun yozilgan edi; asar faqat Buxorodagina emas, balki butun Turkistondagi jadidlar harakatiga ruh va kuch berishi bilan mashhur bo‘ldi”*. [4]

In Fitrat's "Statement of an Indian Tourist", published in Istanbul in 1912, many problems of the life of the country - the poor life of the people, the indiscipline of the military inspectors, the ecological condition of the city and its surrounding villages, the preservation of the people's health - medicine and treatment methods, the poor state of industry and production, the courts work, the need of a national newspaper in several provinces, road construction, even railways, agriculture and handicrafts - all spheres of life are perceived through the eyes of an Indian tourist to be in need of drastic reform. [5] In this work, not only the ideas of reformism, but also the transition to new capitalist relations are promoted. In the work, he explains that religious education in Bukhara madrasas is in a difficult state, the level of knowledge of teachers and students, and the fact that the holy books of Islam are misinterpreted as a result of the shallow knowledge of the Arabic language as follows: *“Madrasamiz bor, kutubxonamiz bor, biroq yurtimizda tafsir va hadisning biror betini, hatto arab tilidan biror betini xatosiz o‘qib, komil ravishda tushuntirib beradigan birorta allomaga ega emasmiz*. [5]

According to Fitrat, as a result of this, the innovations and advanced ideas entering the people's life are condemned as contrary to Sharia. He says: *“Ovro‘podan muallimlar olib kelish va har yili bir necha iste‘dodli yoshlarni tibbiy ta‘lim olish uchun Rossiyaga yuborish, bularning birontasi shariatga qarshi ishlar emas. Zero, olamning faxri bo‘lmish alayhissalavotu vassalla buyurganlar: “Utlub il-ilm va lav bas-Sini”, ya‘ni “ilm agar Chinda bo‘lsa ham tilab o‘qingiz”. Ana shu hadisi sharif mazmuniga diqqat bilan e‘tibor qilaylik, Payg‘ambarimizning Chinni misol keltirishlaridan maqsadlari albatta fiqh va tafsir ilmini o‘rganish*

emas, chunki Chin kofiristondir. Bu hadisda tilga olingan ilm, ya'ni tib va san'atdir. Ma'lum bo'ldiki, dunyoviy ilmlarni g'ayridinlardan o'rganish ham bizning shariatimizga mosdir". [5]

As an enlightened writer, Abdurauf Fitrat put forward the idea of introducing certain reforms in the office of the Bukhara Emirate in "Munozara", while in "Statement of the Indian Tourist" he expresses a new idea - to a certain extent, his objection to the Bukhara Emirate. He does not abandon the ideas of reform, but he cares about the use of the culture, medicine, industry and even underground resources of the Bukhara state for the benefit of the people.

Without Fitrat's work "The Way of Salvation", it is impossible to give a correct assessment of the movement of the Jadids. This work is the only and primary source for evaluating the ideas and goals of the Jadids. The author considers the holy book of Islam, the Holy Qur'an, as the way to save the nation from backwardness. It calls for the unity of the nation around the holy book and the ideas of the Islamic religion. In his opinion, "Holy Qur'an" is knowledge and enlightenment, our forefathers were an example and example for the people of the world in every field, especially knowledge and enlightenment, they knew well the basic essence of each science and used and consumed it well.

Fitrat shows that the main reason why Bukhara is lagging behind in development is the illiteracy of the country's population, the lack of development of political consciousness, and the fact that science is far from enlightenment. He emphasizes the need to develop science in order to save the country from decline and the people from a helpless situation.

Another idea of Fitrat was the idea of uniting the people. In the 25th issue of April 25, 1918, "Hurriyat" newspaper called Turkestans to unite and become one soul for the development of the country and the nation in connection with the new system of administration (Soviet power) established in Russia. The article was ended with this phrases: *"Ey, Turkiston musulmonlari! Tangri uchun, payg'ambar uchun, din uchun, millat uchun keling birlashaylik; oramizdagi shaxsiy tortishmalar, sinfiy*

ayriliqlardan ko'z yumaylik; islom dinining birinchi buyrug'i bo'lgan qardoshlik va ittihad bog'lari bilan bog'lanaylik; qo'lni qo'lga beraylik. Haq yo'linda, din yo'linda, vatan yo'linda, millat yo'linda: jadidimiz, qadimimiz, mullamiz, boyimiz, a'vomimiz bir yerda to'planaylik; bir-birimizga ko'makchi va muovin bo'laylik. Yangi Rusiyaning berdig'i saodati va adolatlaridan foydalanurg'a tirishaylik!..."

[7]

Thus, Fitrat not only published brochures and articles of program importance, but also engaged in practical activities with the main idea underlying these works - enlightenment. Therefore, at the end of 1913 and the beginning of 1914, he was busy with opening a school. Realizing that the goals of the jihadist movement cannot be achieved just by opening new schools, Fitrat came up with demands such as reducing taxes, improving the condition of farmers, ending bribery among officials, and restricting their rights.

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